

THE ROLE OF OPTIONS, FUTURES AND OTHER DERIVATIVES FOR ACCELERATING ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT OF CENTRAL ASIAN COUNTRIES

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Annotation: This article is devoted to the development of the financial market in Central Asia. The economic situation in the states of the region and their competitiveness are also considered. The study used the IMF, WEF, and WB databases, as well as statistics of the EAEU countries. The authors used logical conclusions, the selection of necessary information, and systems analysis when considering the business environment and state regulation measures in the countries of the region. It is noted that the banking sector of Kazakhstan is the most integrated one into the global financial system. Uncertainty in the development of banks in Kyrgyzstan, the isolation of the banking sector in Turkmenistan, and the dependence of credit institutions in Uzbekistan and Tajikistan on administrative intervention are presented. The rates of competitiveness of the financial markets of Central Asian countries are very low – even Kazakhstan, with a fairly developed market of securities, is in 114th place among the 144 countries of the world. Legislation regulating the operation of the stock markets of the Central Asian countries has not yet been formed, Kazakhstan and Kyrgyzstan do not meet international standards, and Tajikistan and Turkmenistan do not officially have stock exchanges. The example of Kazakhstan shows that the capitalization of the stock market is growing, and the stock market ecosystem has been built. The placement of shares of national companies on the London Stock Exchange allowed for the increase of capital, but small trading volumes, an insufficient number of financial instruments, and a limited number of investors hinder the development of the domestic stock market. It is proposed to involve local business structures, enterprises, and the population in investing in socially significant projects through the issuance of municipal bonds.

Keywords: Central Asian countries, competitive, banking sector, financial market, stock exchange.

Modern derivative markets have their intellectual roots in the research of Black, Scholes, and Merton in the early 1970s which then spurred rapid growth as the IT revolution progressed and when two major futures exchanges in Chicago were established. The World Bank and IBM were among the first

institutions that in 1981 developed derivatives and swapped loans of different currencies. The development of derivative instruments then followed two tracks: highly customized interest rate and foreign exchange products were developed by leading financial institutions which created the so-called over-the-counter (OTC) derivatives market. Innovation led to the rapid development of new products, encouraged by minimum regulation and rich profit margins in oligopolistic markets dominated by US banks. In 1993, the Group of Thirty called for the establishment of independent risk oversight, which triggered various legislative initiatives. On the second track, institutional investors were pursuing more standardized equity and commodity products that were traded in more organized and transparent exchanges, starting in Chicago, London, and Tokyo. These exchanges had to be more regulated as retail investors became active market participants.

Introduction. After the collapse of the Soviet Union, Central Asian (CA) countries chose various ways to liberalize the economy, privatize state property, and switch to a market-based management model. They differ in the intensity of their reforms, their management methods, and the degree of centralization of their economies. In the course of time, mistakes in the management of the economy of these countries, border conflicts, and disputes over the solution of water-power problems have worsened the situation and led to strained relations. Today, the region's countries are developing unevenly, and the existing prerequisites for regional economic integration have not been sufficiently used. The countries entered the path of market transformations simultaneously, but today one can see differentiation in the development of financial markets. Kazakhstan is actively implementing reforms in the field of finances: the International Financial Center Astana was created at the international exhibition EXPO-2017 site; the project "People's IPO" is being implemented; and KEGOC, KazTransOil, and Kazatomprom shares are being successfully sold. However, despite the steady growth of GDP, lending in the economy is narrowing, the national currency exchange rate is unstable, and the banking sector is feverish. Uzbekistan has favorable conditions for the development of mineral resource industries. For a long time elements of the planned economy have been preserved, and currently the government is actively involved in the financial sector. The market environment and measures for the development of the banking sector and micro-credit institutions have been formed. Turkmenistan intensively develops agriculture in irrigated oases thanks to the Kara Kum Canal, and has huge resources of gas and oil. The model of the

financial market is one with a significant role of the state in the economy and the strict regulation of private business acts. The country is focused on direct investment, which creates additional demand in the national market. Laws regulating activities in the securities market and the creation of market development institutions have been adopted. Tajikistan is poorly resourced, with the exception of water. In the 1990s the country was engulfed in civil war and remains one of the poorest in the CIS . The budget is supported by remittances from migrant workers working abroad. The government is implementing a system to encourage and facilitate access to portfolio investments and the formation of microfinance institutions.

The prior importance of the Central Asian countries in foreign policy was designated by the President of Uzbekistan immediately after his election and subsequently confirmed by the practical actions and initiatives of our state. Such a policy, aimed at strengthening friendly relations between Uzbekistan and neighboring countries, ensured stability and security on its external borders, which is one of the important conditions for the investment attractiveness of the country. In 2021, the President's Address to the Oliy Majlis, special attention was also paid cooperation with the countries of Central Asia. The President called the priority of this policy "further strengthening of centuries-old friendship, good-neighborly relations, strategic partnership and mutual trust with the states of the region."

According to the initiative of the President, the International Institute of Central Asia was established in Tashkent and on July 15-16 this year, a high-level international conference "Central and South Asia: Regional Interconnectedness. Challenges and Opportunities " was held. The strengthening of regional cooperation was also facilitated by the initiative of the President of Uzbekistan to create a format for annual consultative meetings of countries. The first such meeting was held in Astana in 2018, the second in 2019 in Tashkent, and the third in connection with the pandemic was postponed to the current year.

It is significant that the President also began his first foreign visit in March 2017 from the countries of Central Asia – Turkmenistan and Kazakhstan, followed by trips to Kyrgyzstan and Tajikistan. As part of these visits, business forums were held and significant packages of bilateral intergovernmental agreements on trade, economic and investment cooperation were signed. This contributed to the increase in mutual trade and the development of cooperation ties between Uzbekistan and partners in Central Asia. In addition, the practice of establishing direct contacts between the border regions of Uzbekistan and neighboring

countries, as well as holding regional economic forums was carried out. Subsequent joint visits of the leaders of the Central Asian countries to Uzbekistan consolidated the foundation of multilateral cooperation and expanded the spheres of economic and investment interaction.

Kazakhstan is positioned as a country with a global territory and significant economic potential. Reforms aimed at strengthening budgetary institutions, overcoming the weakness of the banking sector, and modernizing monetary policy in order to maintain low inflation and promote a flexible exchange rate are being actively implemented. Uzbekistan's natural resources contribute to the development of an industrial complex based on natural raw materials. For a long time, the country was dominated by traditional methods of management, and market transformations began only in the last 2–3 years. Currently, the investment environment and measures to encourage investments, including guarantees on the protection of investors' rights, have been formed. Kyrgyzstan has long been the first and only country in the region to join the WTO, which can be seen as a product of its vigorous implementation of early economic reforms. Gold mining at the world's largest Kumtor deposit provides a significant portion of earnings. Mining and power industries are oriented towards exports. Turkmenistan has chosen a hyper-cautious approach to economic reforms as the state's dominant influence in the economy remains. Export and currency control is strictly monitored, which deters foreign investors, and there are no incentives for innovation. Due to high oil and gas prices, export revenues are increasing. Tajikistan is more poorly developed among the Central Asian countries. Experts note the unripe and insufficiently developed legislation, especially surrounding tax, and there are problems with poverty and unemployment. Currently, the authorities are focusing on providing various preferences, attracting benefits from investing money in the hydropower industry and the development of mining. the country. Central Asian countries are not sufficiently integrated into the global financial system. On the one hand, this allows them to neutralize the risks of financial crises. On the other hand, this restricts the flow of foreign capital into these countries. The presence of foreign banks in Kazakhstan and Kyrgyzstan has helped to increase the competitiveness of local banks and improve the competitive environment. At the same time, banks with foreign capital can be agents of external shocks originating from the countries of origin of the head offices.

Conclusion. Central Asian countries will benefit from financial integration. Usually, stock markets win based on the size of the economy, which reduces the

expenses and cost of financial products and develops competition. Regional financial schemes will allow countries to implement interstate projects in the fields of energy industry, water resources, logistics, agriculture, etc. The harmonization of business practice with regulatory systems of the banking and financial sectors will strengthen the investment potential of countries, accelerating the formation of the domestic stock market. All of this will contribute to closer cooperation between the Central Asian States and the free movement of goods, services, capital, and labor.

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